

**POLICY COLLABORATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A DIGITAL
TOURISM VILLAGE BASED ON DISASTER MITIGATION IN RINDU HATI
VILLAGE, CENTRAL BENGKULU REGENCY**

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ABSTRACT

The development of digital villages has become an increasingly urgent policy agenda in Indonesia, particularly in regions with high tourism potential and disaster vulnerability. Rindu Hati Village, located in Central Bengkulu Regency, possesses rich natural and cultural tourism assets but also faces disaster risks and limitations in technological infrastructure and human resource capacity. This condition highlights the necessity of policy collaboration to ensure that digital tourism development is aligned with disaster mitigation efforts. This study aims to analyze the role of collaborative governance in the development of a digital tourism village based on disaster mitigation in Rindu Hati Village. The research employs a qualitative descriptive method, using data collected through in-depth interviews, observations, and document analysis involving local government officials, village authorities, community groups, and other relevant stakeholders. The findings indicate that policy collaboration among government institutions, community organizations, and private actors plays a crucial role in supporting digital tourism initiatives, particularly in strengthening information dissemination, risk awareness, and community participation. However, challenges remain in the form of limited technological readiness, uneven stakeholder commitment, and socio-cultural barriers to digital adoption. Despite these obstacles, collaborative efforts have contributed to increased public awareness of disaster mitigation and improved coordination in tourism village development. The study concludes that effective policy collaboration is essential to ensure the sustainability of digital tourism villages, especially in disaster-prone areas. Strengthening institutional synergy, enhancing community capacity, and integrating disaster mitigation into digital tourism policies are key recommendations for future development.

Keywords: Digital Village, Disaster Mitigation, Policy Collaboration.